

Compact Antipodal Vivaldi Antennas for Body Area Communication

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, compact on-body antipodal Vivaldi antennas (AVAs) are proposed for body area network (BAN), which work at the lower ultra-wide-band (UWB). The antennas are modified by employing the tapered slot edge (TSE) to lower the resonance frequency and improve the radiation characteristics. In order to increase the gain of antenna further so that improve the transmission efficiency from in-body to on-body, two compact on-body AVA arrays are designed operating at the lower UWB. The polarization of the two antenna arrays are linear and mutually perpendicular with each other. In addition, each of antenna arrays are composed of four single elements which are fed by optimized 1×4 Wilkinson power divider. The performance of S_{11} and far field patterns show that the operating band of the antenna arrays covers the lower UWB band, which signifies that the benefits of introducing TSE to lower the resonance frequency is obvious. Furthermore, the influence of the human body on antenna array is discussed and the results satisfies the requirement of in-body to on-body communication.

CCS Concepts

• CCS → Hardware → Communication hardware, interfaces and storage → Wireless devices

• CCS → Human-centered computing → Ubiquitous and mobile computing → Ubiquitous and mobile devices → Personal digital assistants

Keywords

Implanted antenna; Impedance characteristics; Far-field boundary; Phase error.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing research interest in BAN for medical and healthcare devices, the demand for miniaturized and high-efficiency electronic devices is increasing. Many kinds of BAN applications have been proposed, especially, one of the most interesting area is wireless capsule endoscope (WCE). In order to achieve high data rate and real-time video imaging transform for

communicating between implanted and wearable devices, the UWB is the feasible operating frequency band for the transmitter and receiver systems. The co-authors have designed a wearable dual-polarized antenna array for in-body to on-body UWB communication [1]. To reduce the dimensions and increase the gain of antenna array, a modified AVA array has been proposed.

In this paper, the polarization of the designed two antenna arrays are linear and mutually perpendicular with each other. And each of antenna arrays are composed of four single elements which are fed by optimized 1×4 Wilkinson power divider. TSE is employed to reduce the dimensions and increase the gain and radiation efficiency. To obtain strong broadside radiation, a metallic reflector is positioned above the antenna array, and the distance between antenna and reflector is optimized. Based on the proposed idea, a full EM wave simulation has been implemented to get the retain loss and far field patterns of antenna arrays. In addition to that, the influence of human body on the antenna is also investigated. Different separation distance between the antenna array and human body dramatically influence the performance of the antenna. Finally, the optimized parameters of antenna array are proposed to improve the transmission efficiency for in-body to on-body communication.

2. Modified antipodal Vivaldi antenna

As the first step, conventional AVA is designed as shown in Fig. 1(a). For this type of Vivaldi antenna, the two layers are positioned on the opposite sides of the substrate. The antenna is fed by a simple microstrip line which is conveniently achieve 50Ω matching. In order to reduce the dimensions and make the antenna independent of the influence of the human body, large permittivity substrate is employed, which is Rogers RO 3010 (thickness = 0.25mm, $\epsilon_r = 10.2$). The dimensions of the antenna is 40 mm \times 45 mm, and the width of the feed line is 0.28 mm.

Fig. 1(b) shows the modified AVA. On each patch surface, a pair of TSE is etched, each TSE is composed of two circular arcs, this idea is extension to the work of the report of Peng and Yong [2-3]. The configuration takes full use of the path area and eliminates the current discontinuity on the edges and the parameters of arcs are optimized to satisfy the lowest-frequency requirement. Through employing TSE on the surface of the antenna to miniature the size of antenna and improve the current distribution at the edges of the antenna so that the front to back ratio is improved and the radiation efficiency can be increased and resonance can be shift to lower frequency.

Fig.2 illustrates the S_{11} variation of conventional AVA and TSE AVA. As shown in Fig. 2, the lower-end resonance frequency of conventional AVA is 4.2 GHz, which doesn't satisfy the requirement of UWB band. For the TSE AVA, without enlarging the dimension of the antenna, TSE is employed to shift the frequency to 2.8GHz, which fits/satisfies the S_{11} lower UWB band

As Table. 1 shows, the whole dimensions of the original AVA and TSE AVA remain the same. Taking the electric size into account, for the original AVA, the dimensions are set to be 40×45 mm, which is approximately $0.56 \lambda \times 0.63 \lambda$, which is the wavelength of 4.2GHz (the low end). In addition, for the TSE AVA, it is set to be the wave wavelength of 2.8GHz, thus the dimension is approximately $0.3 \lambda \times 0.42 \lambda$. Evidently, TSE is able to miniaturize the size of the antenna by lowering the minimum operating frequency.

Figure 1. Designed antipodal Vivaldi antenna. (a) Original AVA (b) Modified AVA with tapered slot edge.

Table 1. Parameters of AVA and modified AVA

Parameters	Length / mm
L1	45
W1	40
L2	45
W2	40

Figure 2. S_{11} performance of original AVA and TSE AVA

The pattern of AVA can be seen from Fig. 4, which shows that the direction of pattern is along the plane of antenna. The realized

gains varying with frequency of original AVA and TSE AVA are shown in Fig. 3. During the band between 3GHz to 5GHz, the minimum realized gain of TSE AVA is 3.8dB, and the maximum is 5.3dB. Compared with the realized gain of original AVA, which is from 1.1dB to 3.7dB between 3GHz to 5GHz, the benefit of TSE to increase gain is prominent. The deteriorative behavior presenting in Fig. 3 is possibly caused by the irregular current along the edge of slot, especially at the high frequency (above 8GHz), which can be accepted as the compensation for the low-end performance.

Figure 3. Realized gain performance of original AVA and TSE AVA

Figure 4. Far field pattern of AVA and TSE AVA at 4 GHz

For the wireless capsule endoscope, the on-body antenna communicates with the implanted antenna, turning the direction of field pattern to be perpendicular to the plane of the antenna could further the transmission efficiency. A reflector can be employed to lead to turn the direction of the pattern and gain enhancement of the antenna by reflecting the antenna backlash energy back. In theory, the antenna gain can be increased by 3dB, but the antenna distance from the reflector cannot be too close, otherwise, the mirror current radiation will offset the antenna radiation so that the radiation characteristics of the antenna are deteriorated. Since the plane wave perpendicularly incident on the surface of the ideal conductor producing an 180 degree phase difference, the reflector is usually placed at least a quarter of the wavelength from the antenna, then the phase difference of 180 degrees by the antenna radiation to the reflector and then reflected to the antenna path difference can offset the 180 degrees phase difference generated by the reflector.

Fig. 5 is TSE AVA with metallic reflector. And the distance between antenna and reflector is 20mm. From Fig. 6, after introducing the reflector, the S11 performance becomes deteriorated, especially between 3.2GHz to 3.7GHz, which is possibly due to the reflected wave coupling with slot to disturb the current distribution. Despite all this, the deteriorated S11 can be accepted as compensation of gain enhancement.

Figure 5. TSE antipodal Vivaldi antenna with the reflector.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. S11 performances of TSE AVA with and without reflector (a) 1-10GHz, (b) 3-5GHz

Figure 7. Far-field pattern of TSE AVA with reflector (Realized Gain 3GHz: 7.6 dB, 4GHz: 9.8 dB, 5GHz: 10.6 dB)

As shown in Fig. 7, the direction of far-field pattern is perpendicular to the plane of the antenna, and the realized gain raises up to 7.6 dB to 10.6 dB at the lower band of UWB (3GHz-5GHz) comparing with the antenna without reflector whose realized gain is from 3.8 dB to 5.3 dB.

3. Antipodal Vivaldi antenna array (horizontal and vertical polarization)

For the purpose of facilitating the increase of the gain of antenna further, the AVA arrays are designed, which are shown in Fig. 8. In the WCE application senior, due to the unfixed of position and direction of the implanted antenna in abdomen, thus the polarization of wave transforming from in-body to on-body is unascertained. Due to every polarizations can be decomposed to horizontal and vertical polarizations, two mutually perpendicular linear polarizations can be utilized as the receiving to maximize the recieved power.

As Fig. 8 shows, Wilkinson power divider is designed to combine the four antennas. In addition, the dimension of the power divider is miniaturized to conform the requirement of on-body antennas. The width of the Wilkinson power divider is 35.62mm, and the length is determined by the interval of each antenna. For the horizontal and vertical polarization array, the interval is separately 40mm and 70mm, thus the lengths are 200 mm and 280 mm. For the vertical polarization array, in order to eliminate the coupling of each antenna, the interval is set at 70mm which is the approximate wavelength of center frequency 4GHz. Moreover, two 100-ohm isolation resistances are soldered to the power divider to further isolation and enlarge antenna gain.

Figure 8. Antipodal Vivaldi antenna arrays (a) Horizontal polarization (b) Vertical polarization

The S11 performances of the two arrays are shown in Fig. 9. In the band of 3GHz to 5GHz, the S11 approximately satisfies the requirement of less than -10 dB, which can be accepted as the competence of gain enlargement and turning pattern direction. Obviously from Fig. 10, a reflector is employed to give the antenna backlash energy back and turn the direction of the pattern. The realized gain of the horizontal polarization array is from 9.5 to 12.3dB, and the pattern is perpendicular to the antenna array. Meanwhile, for the vertical polarization array, the realized gain is from 12.5 to 7.8dB, the relatively decreasing trend of the gain is due to the large interval of each antenna with respect to the wavelength of high frequency.

Figure 9. S11 performance of Antipodal Vivaldi antenna arrays

Figure 10. Far-field patterns of AVA arrays (a) Horizontal polarization (b) Vertical polarization

4. The influence of human body on antipodal Vivaldi antenna

The permittivity of the human body is high with respect to the free space so that it will affect the antenna a lot with the distance varying between the antenna and the human body, as Fig. 11 shows. The dielectric characteristics of the human body torso in lower UWB band can be approximated using an average muscle tissue. The average dielectric parameters for human torso tissue in the lower UWB band can be approximated as an average dielectric constant of 51.5 and average conductivity of 3.2 S/m. As shown in Fig. 11, the simulation configuration is that AVA with reflector is put on the human body and the distance between the human body and AVA is varied to acquire the different S11 results. The S11 performance is shown in Fig. 12.

The S11 performance of AVA with metallic reflector is significantly influenced by the distance. As shown in Fig.12, the requirement of S11 less than -10dB is fulfilled under the condition that the distance is 2mm. With distance raising up to 7mm, the deterioration of S11 becomes prominent. Owing to the influence of human body becoming less when the distance between antenna and human body gets enough large, the S11 starts to get better.

Figure 11. AVA with reflector on human body

Figure 12. S11 performance of AVA with reflector varying with the distance between antenna and human body

In conclusion, the AVA array with reflector should be as close as possible to the human body to minimize the S11. In addition, for wireless capsule endoscope application, the on-body antenna should be close to the human body to maximize the receiving power. Thus, the distance between the array and human body is set as 2mm. From Fig. 13, the S11 performances of horizontal and vertical polarization array fulfill the requirement.

Figure 13. S11 performance of horizontal and vertical polarization antenna arrays

5. Measurement Results

The antennas are fabricated on 10-mil-thick Rogers 3010 substrate, for fixing the metallic reflector on the back, a piece of polyurethane foam is attached on, as Fig. 14. The measurement and simulation S11 in free space is shown in Fig 15. It can be seen that the measurement and simulation results are similar with each other, especially in the lower UWB band. The ripples of the measurement results are introduced by the connector. And the antenna is measurement on the chest, the results are shown in Fig. 16. The lowest resonance frequency of antenna is extended to 1.5 GHz as the measurement results. Therefore, the antenna with optimized taper slot edge can dramatical improve the impedance bandwidth without increasing the dimensions of antenna.

Figure 14. Fabricated TSE AVA. (a) Signal antenna (b) Antenna array

(a)

(b)

Figure. 15 Measurement and simulated S11 results of signal AVA array in free space (a) 1 – 10 GHz (b) 3 – 5 GHz

(a)

(b)

Figure. 16 Measurement and simulated S11 results on body. (a) 1 – 10 GHz (b) 3 – 5 GHz

The measurement results of antenna arrays in free space and on human body are shown in Fig. 17 and 18. It can be seen that the S11 performance on human body is better than that in free space, this is because that the antenna array is optimized on human body. In the lower UWB band, the measured S11 lower UWB

performancing on human body is less than -10, which satisfies the requirement of BAN application.

(a)

(b)

Figure. 17 Measurement and simulated S11 results of antenna array in free space. (a) 1 – 10 GHz (b) 3 – 5 GHz

(a)

Figure. 18 Measurement and simulated S11 results of antenna array on human body. (a) 1 – 10 GHz (b) 3 – 5 GHz

6. Conclusion

The paper proposes compact on-body antipodal Vivaldi antennas operating at the lower UWB. By introducing the taper slot edge to the antenna, the lowest frequency can be lowered and the antenna achieve compact geometry, meanwhile the radiation efficiency is improved. In order to improve the transmission efficiency from in-body to on-body, two AVA antenna arrays are designed. The polarizations of the two antenna arrays are linear and mutually perpendicular with each other. And the metallic reflector has been

added to turn the direction of patterns and reflect the antenna backlash energy back. Moreover, the influence of human body on antenna is investigated to optimize the performance of antenna arrays as on-body receiving antenna. It shows that when be put on the human body, the antenna arrays work well. The measurement results also are shown to illustrate the performance of antenna.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is supported by "WiBEC" (Wireless In-Body Environment) project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 675353.

8. REFERENCES

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